

Studies on Solutions of High Dielectric Constant: Part XI. Solubilities of some Electrolytes in N-Methylacetamide at Different Temperatures

Dinesh Chandra and Ram Gopal

In continuation with the previous work¹ on the solubilities of common electrolytes in formamide, it was considered desirable and useful to extend the study to other non-aqueous solvents of high dielectric constant belonging to the formamide group. N-methylacetamide (NMA) has a very high dielectric constant. ($\approx 171^2$ at 35°) and a large dipole moment ($\approx 3.78D^3$). It is fairly stable and can be easily purified. Hence it was our next choice. Although approximate solubilities of some electrolytes have been reported⁴ at 40° in NMA, a systematic investigation on these lines does not appear to have ever been attempted. This situation has prompted the investigation reported in this communication.

EXPERIMENTAL

NMA was dried over freshly ignited quicklime and then distilled under reduced pressure. The middle fraction of the distillate was collected and fractionally crystallised twice. It was again distilled under reduced pressure; its electrical conductance was found to be about 10^{-6} mho; and was used without further purification. Solutes were purified by repeated crystallization. The other experimental details, including the precautions and arrangements for avoiding moisture were, more or less, the same as detailed in the previous communication.¹ The temperature of the thermostat was controlled to within $\pm 0.05^\circ$ in the lower temperature range ($35-40^\circ$) and $\pm 0.1^\circ$ in the upper range ($45-50^\circ$). After stirring the solvent and solute in the solubility flask for over 5 to 6 hours with an electric stirrer in a thermostat at the desired temperature, the solute was allowed to settle. The time required for settling of the solute was considerably longer due to the viscous nature of the solvent. Three samples of the clear saturated solution, at successive intervals after extra stirrings, were withdrawn with a pipette and were analysed by (a) careful evaporation of the solvent or (b) by appropriate precipitation of the solute, as described previously¹. From the data obtained, the solubilities were calculated in gms. of solute in 100 gms. NMA. The deviation from the mean value were less than $\pm 0.5\%$ in most cases. The values of solubilities, thus obtained, are recorded in Table I.

The solubilities obtained by Dawson⁴ are recorded in cases where available for the sake of comparison. The data recorded in Table I should be treated with reserve. Since the experiments have to be continued for long intervals of time and so the solvent may

1. Gopal and Husain, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 272.
2. Bass *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 509; Lin and Dannhauser, *Ibid*, 1963, **67**, 1805.
3. Meighan and Cole, *Ibid*, 1964, **68**, 503.
4. Dawson *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1963, **67**, 281.

decompose slightly, specially at the high temperatures. All the same, it is believed that the data obtained are good enough for a qualitative study of the solute-solvent interaction in NMA which is the principal aim of the present series of investigations.

TABLE I

Solubilities of some electrolytes in NMA at different temperatures

Solubilities in gms. of solute in 100 gms. of NMA at

Solute	32°	35°	40°	45°	50°
NaCl	2.054	2.075	2.109 (2.104*)	2.144	2.182
NaBr	19.080	19.160	19.231 (20.20*)	19.312	19.421
NaI	51.482	53.301	56.273 (45.51*)	29.230	62.322
NaNO ₃	12.370	12.572	12.981 (5.864*)	13.290	13.621
KCl	0.865	0.899	0.958 (0.9496*)	1.007	1.071
KBr	4.773	4.862	5.003 (5.430*)	5.142	5.278
KI	30.430	30.682	31.161 (32.57*)	31.689	32.278
KNO ₃	2.518	2.584	2.686 (2.684*)	2.675	2.823
K ₂ SO ₄	0.230	0.245	0.269 (0.5540*)	0.293	0.3170
NH ₄ Cl	4.883	4.967	5.093 (5.083*)	5.221	5.353
NH ₄ Br	21.861	21.959	22.112 (18.13*)	22.261	22.430
(NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	1.045	1.098	1.165	1.237	1.308
BaCl ₂	12.471	12.728	13.231	13.729	14.170
BaBr ₂	38.502	38.810	39.428 (23.12*)	40.061	40.668
Ba(NO ₃) ₂	13.440	13.678	14.131 (9.986*)	14.549	15.040
SrCl ₂	16.131	16.632	17.468	18.220	19.342
SrBr ₂	41.499	42.121	43.040 (43.07*)	43.949	44.901
Sr(NO ₃) ₂	25.341	26.022	27.140 (15.92*)	28.191	29.240
MnSO ₄	0.258	0.277	0.309	0.343	0.377
PbCl ₂	1.429	1.502	1.661	1.822	1.982
PbBr ₂	7.519	7.861	8.543	9.170	9.849
Pb(NO ₃) ₂	82.990	84.979	87.931	90.891	93.730

*Figures in parantheses are Dawson's values.

DISCUSSION

It may be noted from Table I that there is a close agreement between the data obtained by Dawson⁴ and those found in the present investigation in many cases like NaCl, NaBr, KCl, KBr, KI, KNO₃, NH₄Cl and SrBr₂, although there is a good deal of divergence

in cases like NaI, NaNO₃, K₂SO₄, NH₄Br, BaBr₂, Ba(NO₃)₂ and Sr(NO₃)₂. It is difficult to account for the difference. However, Dawson's values are, on his own admission, approximate and have been obtained from the conductance measurements. This method may be questionable except for sparingly soluble substances. Generally, solubilities are in the same order as in water viz., Iodides > Bromides > Chlorides and the sulphates are only slightly soluble. Further, the solubilities are, in general, lower in NMA than those in water but are similar to those in formamide¹, the values in NMA being somewhat lower for the uni-univalent electrolytes.

In view of the further work on the solubilities of electrolytes in other solvents of this group, in progress in this laboratory, it is advisable to withhold further comments until a general picture emerges after completion of the investigation.

Our thanks are due to Prof. A. B. Sen, Head of the Chemistry Department, for the grant of a R.T.S. to one of us (D.C.). We also appreciate the assistance of Dr. M. M. Husain which he ungrudgingly extended during the course of this investigation. The work has been possible due to availability of NMA in sufficient quantity, purchased from grants of C.S.I.R. (India) and the Society of Sigma Xi and RESA of U.S.A., to whom authors are very much grateful.

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
LUCKNOW UNIVERSITY.

Received, January 4, 1968.